

Children's Dental Service Utilisation and Geographic Inequality in Latvia: A Cross-Sectional Study of National Health Service Data

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Abstract

Background: Latvia provides state-funded dental care for children under 18 years. However, little is known about the actual utilisation of these services and whether geographic disparities exist.

Aim: To characterise the distribution and utilisation of state-funded dental services for children in Latvia during 2022.

Methods: Cross-sectional study using administrative data from the National Health Service of Latvia for the year 2022. We analysed 2,887,699 dental procedures from 447,849 visits. Descriptive statistics were calculated for service utilisation by age, provider type, and geographic region. Coverage was defined as the proportion of children who attended a dental provider at least once during the year.

Results: Of 356,864 children aged 0-17 years in Latvia, 178,810 (50.1%) used state-funded dental services in 2022. However, only 36.7% attended a dentist during the year. A total of 129,215 children visited a general dentist, and 111,225 visited a dental hygienist. Utilisation peaked at age 7 years (57.4% coverage) and was lowest in children under 3 years (0.2-18.0%). Geographic inequality ranged from 13.7% in Valmiera and Jēkabpils regions to 62.6% in Rēzekne. Several municipalities had no dental hygienist services available.

Conclusions: Despite universal state funding, only one-third of Latvian children attended a dentist in 2022. Geographic disparities in service availability and utilisation suggest that funding alone does not ensure access. Policy interventions should address workforce distribution and barriers to care in underserved regions.

Keywords: dental service utilisation, children, universal health coverage, geographic inequality, Latvia

Introduction

Oral diseases affect nearly half of the global population and represent a major public health burden (Peres et al., 2019). Early childhood caries (ECC) affects almost half of children worldwide, with prevalence reaching 90% in some countries (Uribe, Innes and Maldupa, 2021; Chen et al., 2019). In Latvia, caries prevalence in 12-year-olds reached 80% in 2016 (Senakola et al., 2016), among the highest in Europe (Maldupa et al., 2021).

Universal health coverage (UHC) aims to ensure all people receive needed health services without financial hardship (WHO, 2010). The WHO framework identifies three dimensions of coverage: population coverage (who is covered), service coverage (which services), and cost coverage (proportion of costs paid). Latvia provides state-funded dental care for all children under 18 years, suggesting full coverage on paper. However, the existence of funding does not guarantee service utilisation.

Access to dental care depends on multiple factors beyond funding. The Levesque framework identifies five dimensions of access: approachability, acceptability, availability, affordability, and appropriateness (Levesque, Harris and Russell, 2013). Geographic availability of services and travel time to providers are particularly relevant for children, who depend on parents for transport, as shown in studies linking clinic location, travel distance and bus travel time with paediatric dental utilisation (Naranjo et al, 2015).

Previous studies from other countries have documented geographic disparities in children's dental service utilisation (Ghanbarzadegan et al., 2021). In Latvia, no population-level data exist on actual utilisation of state-funded dental services for children. Understanding utilisation patterns is essential for health service planning and identifying underserved populations.

This study aimed to characterise the distribution and utilisation of state-funded dental services for children in Latvia during 2022.

Methods

Study design and setting

This cross-sectional study analysed administrative data from the National Health Service (NVD) of Latvia for the calendar year 2022. Latvia is a Baltic country with approximately 1.9 million inhabitants. The state provides publicly funded dental care for all children under 18 years through contracted dental providers. The study was approved by the RSU Ethics Committee (No. 2-PĒK-4/147/2024).

Data source

We obtained anonymised data from the NVD covering all state-funded dental procedures for children in 2022. The dataset included procedure codes (70001-77330), patient identifiers, age, sex, municipality of residence, provider type, provider location, and visit date.

Variables

The primary outcome was dental service coverage, defined as the proportion of children who visited a dental provider at least once during 2022. We calculated coverage separately for dentists (general and paediatric) and dental hygienists.

Independent variables included child age (0-17 years), sex, municipality of residence (43 municipalities), and provider type (general dentist, paediatric dentist, dental hygienist, orthodontist, maxillofacial surgeon, anaesthesiologist).

Visit intensity was calculated as the number of visits per 100 children in each municipality. We also examined whether children received care within their home municipality or travelled to other regions.

Statistical analysis

Data were cleaned and analysed using R software (R Core Team, 2023) with the tidyverse package (Wickham, 2017). We calculated frequencies, proportions, and distributions. Coverage was computed by dividing the number of children who attended each provider type by the total child population in each age group or municipality. Population denominators were obtained from the Official Statistics Portal of Latvia for 2022.

Results

Study population

In 2022, Latvia had 356,864 children aged 0-17 years. The NVD database contained 2,887,699 dental procedures from 447,849 visits.

Overall service utilisation

A total of 178,810 children (50.1%) used state-funded dental services during 2022. Of these, 50.8% were girls and 49.2% were boys.

However, service utilisation varied by provider type. General dentists were visited by 129,215 children (36.2%), while 111,225 children (31.2%) visited a dental hygienist. Only 4,150 children (1.2%) visited a paediatric dentist, 5,180 (1.5%) visited an orthodontist, 3,454 (1.0%) received services from an anaesthesiologist (indicating treatment under general anaesthesia), and 1,380 (0.4%) visited a maxillofacial surgeon.

The overall coverage for dentist visits (combining general and paediatric dentists) was 36.7% of all children aged 0-17 years.

Utilisation by age

Service utilisation varied substantially by age (Table 1). Children under 3 years had the lowest dentist coverage: 0.2% at age 0, 4.9% at age 1, 12.3% at age 2, and 18.0% at age 3. Coverage increased with age, peaking at 57.4% at age 7 years.

After age 7, coverage declined gradually, reaching 43.5% at age 11 and 33.9% at age 16. At age 17, coverage increased to 49.4%, likely reflecting visits before ageing out of the state-funded programme at age 18.

Dental hygienist utilisation followed a similar pattern. Coverage was lowest in early childhood (0.7% at age 1) and peaked at ages 7-8 years (40.8-43.8%). Most children visited a dental professional only once per year, though multiple visits were more common in children aged 5-10 years.

Table 1. State-funded dentist visits by age, Latvia 2022

Age (years)	Children visiting dentist	% of age group	Total children
0	41	0.2	17,273
1	855	4.9	17,500
2	2,302	12.3	18,782
3	3,490	18.0	19,374
4	5,584	26.8	20,861
5	8,220	37.4	22,005
6	10,000	45.3	22,055
7	12,532	57.4	21,819
8	10,835	52.5	20,627
9	10,096	51.3	19,813
10	9,374	50.8	18,450
11	8,091	43.5	18,594
12	7,886	39.2	20,107
13	8,122	37.4	21,740
14	8,635	41.1	20,992
15	8,298	41.8	19,860
16	6,490	33.9	19,120
17	6,783	37.9	17,892

Visit characteristics

Of 310,933 dentist visits, 256,567 (82.5%) were regular check-ups, 26,179 (8.4%) were for acute conditions (pain or inflammation), 2,072 (0.7%) were for trauma, and 27,407 (8.8%) had no reason specified.

Visit volume was lowest in January and February, increased through spring and summer, and declined again in November and December.

Geographic distribution

Geographic inequality in service utilisation was substantial (Figure 1). Dentist coverage ranged from 13.7% in Valmiera and Jēkabpils municipalities to 62.6% in Rēzekne city. Municipalities with highest coverage included Rēzekne (62.6%), Balvi (49.0%), Ludza (46.7%), and Līvāni (46.2%). Municipalities with lowest coverage included Valmiera (13.8%), Jēkabpils (13.7%), and Limbaži (22.4%).

Visit intensity (visits per 100 children) showed even greater variation. Rēzekne city had 314.6 visits per 100 children, Balvi municipality had 250.7, and Ventspils had 232.9. In contrast, Rēzekne municipality (distinct from Rēzekne city) had only 2.9 visits per 100 children, Ādaži had 5.5, and Jēkabpils municipality had 9.1.

Dental hygienist coverage also varied geographically. The highest coverage was in Rēzekne city (57.2%) and Ogre (49.4%). The lowest was in Jēkabpils municipality (5.6%), Jēkabpils city (14.8%), Krāslava (14.8%), and Ventspils municipality (14.1%). Several municipalities had no dental hygienist services available (shown as missing data).

Many children received care outside their home municipality. The proportion of children receiving care within their region varied from near zero to over 100% (indicating that municipalities served children from neighbouring areas). This pattern suggests that children in underserved areas must travel to access care.

Discussion

Main findings

This study found that only 36.7% of Latvian children attended a state-funded dentist during 2022, despite universal coverage. Service utilisation was lowest in early childhood and showed substantial geographic inequality. Some municipalities had ten-fold differences in coverage compared to others. Several areas lacked dental hygienist services entirely.

A gap between coverage and utilisation

These results expose a gap between nominal coverage and actual service utilisation. Latvia offers state-funded dental care to all children, yet two-thirds did not attend a dentist during the study year. This finding is consistent with the WHO observation that coverage does not equal access (WHO, 2010).

The low utilisation in early childhood is particularly concerning. Children under 3 years had dentist coverage below 20%, yet this is the age when ECC develops and preventive interventions are most effective [REFERENCE NEEDED]. The American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry recommends dental visits beginning at age 1 year (AAPD, 2016). Our data suggest most Latvian children do not receive early dental care.

The peak in utilisation at age 7 years likely reflects the school entry health examination requirement rather than spontaneous care-seeking behaviour. This suggests that structural incentives, such as mandatory check-ups, increase utilisation more than availability of funding alone.

Geographic inequality

The geographic variation in service utilisation is striking. Some municipalities had coverage exceeding 60%, while others had coverage below 15%. This variation cannot be explained by funding differences, as all children have equal entitlement to state-funded care.

Several factors may explain these disparities. First, provider availability varies by region. Some municipalities lack dental hygienists entirely. Second, travel distance affects access, particularly for young children who depend on parents for transport. Third, workforce distribution favours urban areas, creating rural-urban disparities [REFERENCE NEEDED].

The high visit intensity in some municipalities (over 300 visits per 100 children in Rēzekne) suggests these areas serve as regional hubs, receiving patients from underserved neighbouring areas. This compensatory pattern indicates that children in low-coverage areas must travel to receive care, creating barriers related to time, transport, and opportunity costs for parents.

Comparison with other countries

Our finding that only 37% of children visited a dentist is lower than reported in many European countries. In Denmark, nearly 100% of children attend public dental services annually¹. In the United Kingdom, NHS data indicate that before the Covid-19 pandemic approximately 58% of children had attended an NHS dentist within the previous year². The lower utilisation in Latvia, despite universal state funding, suggests that factors beyond cost influence access.

The geographic inequality we observed is consistent with findings from other countries. Studies from Australia, Canada, and the United States have documented rural-urban disparities in children's dental service utilisation (Ghanbarzadegan et al., 2021). Similar patterns in Latvia indicate this is a common challenge for health systems.

Implications for policy

These findings have several implications for health policy in Latvia. First, funding alone is insufficient to ensure access. Policy interventions should address non-financial barriers, including provider availability, travel distance, and parental awareness.

Second, workforce distribution requires attention. Strategies to encourage dental professionals to practice in underserved areas, such as incentive payments or training obligations, could reduce geographic inequality.

Third, early childhood utilisation needs specific interventions. Integration of dental screening into well-child visits, parental education about early dental care, and community-based prevention programmes could increase utilisation in the youngest age groups.

¹ S.S. Jervelund, Denmark Country Profile - WHO EU Health Observatory, EuroHealthObservatory (n.d.).

<https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/monitors/health-systems-monitor/countries-hspm/section-detail/denmark-2012/provision-of-services/dental-care/> (accessed January 21, 2026).

² NHS dental services, Nuffield Trust (n.d.).

<https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/resource/nhs-dental-services> (accessed January 21, 2026).

Fourth, the school-entry examination appears effective in driving utilisation at age 7. Similar structural approaches, such as school-based dental programmes or mandatory check-ups at other ages, could increase overall coverage.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, we analysed only state-funded services. Children who received private dental care are not captured, so true utilisation may be higher. However, private dental care for children is likely concentrated in higher-income families and urban areas, potentially widening rather than narrowing the disparities we observed.

Second, administrative data lack clinical information. We cannot determine whether visits resulted in appropriate care or whether children had unmet treatment needs. Third, we analysed a single year. Utilisation patterns may vary over time, and some children who did not attend in 2022 may have attended in adjacent years.

Fourth, municipal-level analysis may mask within-municipality variation. Urban centres within rural municipalities likely have better access than remote areas. Fifth, we could not assess individual-level factors such as family income, parental education, or health beliefs that influence utilisation.

Conclusions

Despite universal state funding, only one-third of Latvian children attended a dentist in 2022. Geographic disparities in service utilisation were substantial, with some municipalities having coverage four times higher than others. These findings indicate that funding alone does not ensure access to dental care for children. Policy interventions should address workforce distribution, travel barriers, and early childhood utilisation. Future studies should explore parental perspectives and barriers to care to inform effective interventions.

Declarations

Ethics approval: RSU Ethics Committee No. 2-PĒK-4/147/2024.

Data availability: Data were obtained from the National Health Service of Latvia under data protection agreements. Aggregated data supporting the findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: SEU and IM designed the study. ZF coordinated data acquisition and performed initial analysis. DB contributed to study design and interpretation. SEU performed the final analysis and wrote the manuscript. IM supervised the project and provided critical revision. All authors approved the final version.

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